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From Legal Impossibilism to the Rule of Law Crisis: Transitional Justice and Polish Counter- Constitutionalism

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Abstract:

Since 2015 the Law and Justice government has significantly altered the composition of the Polish Constitutional Court, the Supreme Court, and the National Council of Judiciary. It has also expanded the power of the executive branch in relation to the courts. This process – which the majority of scholars and legal practitioners see as a period of deterioration of the rule of law – also has a transitional justice dimension. In this paper, I claim that the decline of Polish liberal constitutionalism was possible because the current government managed to create an alternative constitutional vision – a counter-constitution, to borrow the term from Kim Lane Scheppele. The cornerstone of this counter-constitutionalism is the belief in ‘legal impossibilism’: strict constitutional constraints supposedly preventing the parliamentary majority from introducing crucial reforms, including mechanisms for dealing with the communist past. The analysis of the Polish constitutional framework demonstrates that ‘legal impossibilism’ perceived this way is a myth. However, under closer scrutiny and contrary to popular assumptions, in the transitional justice domain ‘legal impossibilism’ becomes interpreted by those currently in power not as restrictions preventing any reckoning with the communist past. Instead, it appears as restraints upon a radical shake-up in political, social, and economic hierarchies. For this government, without such a change the democratic transformation remains incomplete.

KEYWORDS: transitional justice, constitutional crisis, counter-constitutionalism, legal impossibilism, constitutional sociology

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From Legal Impossibilism to the Rule of Law Crisis: Transitional Justice and Polish Counter-Constitutionalism

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1. Introduction

In contemporary liberal democracies, there is a tension between the democratic element, which demands that the sphere of political decision-making be as large as possible, and the liberal component, which sees some rights as inherent and some norms as inviolable, and therefore not open to debate. The tension exists not only because the majority may use the democratic process in a way that infringes on the rights of an individual or a minority, but also because constitutional provisions designed to divide the power between the branches of government and to protect human rights regulate the political process and limit the scope and content of political decisions.¹ Thus, as Wiktor Osiatyński puts it, ‘the more there is in the constitution, the less room there remains for democracy and for compromises within society and, consequently, the less power for parliament and more power for those courts in which constitutional claims are settled’.² However, one may also argue that this conflict exists not between constitutionalism and democracy, but lies internally within constitutionalism itself. According to Paul Blokker, contemporary constitutionalism is informed by two conflicting imaginaries. A dominant modernist one sees constitutions as regulatory instruments which impose stability and order and are closely related to ideas such as state sovereignty, rational social engineering and universal norms and values. On the other hand, democratic imaginary is connected to notions such as self-government, autonomy, creativity and indeterminacy.³ While the former vision serves as a base of legal constitutionalism, the latter imaginary is closely connected to its political counterpart.

According to some interpretations, Polish constitutional crisis can be seen as yet another example of the tensions between legal and political constitutionalism. Since 2015, the Law and Justice government has significantly altered the composition of the Polish Constitutional Court (“PCC”), the Supreme Court (“SC”), and the National Council of Judiciary and expanded the power of executive branch in relation to the courts. Even though many Polish legal scholars see this period as a time of ‘anti-constitutional populist backsliding’⁴ during which the multidimensional assault on the rule of law has caused Poland to become a constitutional

¹ See eg András Sajó, *Limiting Government: An Introduction to Constitutionalism* (Central European University Press 1999) 49-68; Wiktor Osiatyński, *Human Rights and their Limits* (CUP 2009) 72-81.

² Osiatyński (n 1) 79.

³ Paul Blokker, ‘The Imaginary Constitution of Constitutions’ (2019) 1 *Social Imaginaries* 167.

⁴ Wojciech Sadurski, *Poland’s Constitutional Breakdown* (OUP 2019) (hereafter ‘Sadurski, *Poland’s*’).

pariah,⁵ alternative interpretations are also present. Adam Czarnota claims that the actions of the current government can be seen as a ‘necessary adjustment of the system implanted in this part of the world after 1989’⁶: a change aimed at curbing ‘an excess of legal constitutionalism which was definitely anti-democratic in its nature’.⁷ Thus, for Czarnota the crisis has a ‘democratic, emancipatory potential’: it is a turn towards political constitutionalism and a search for an independent constitutional identity promoting the rule of ‘a political nation’ and ‘dejuridisation’ of the public sphere.⁸ Other authors, even if they also explain the crisis in terms of the clash between the liberal and the political component of a democratic system,⁹ do not share this optimism. As Maciej Pichlak aptly observes, this so-called ‘democratization’ is superficial in nature and boils down to bolstering the role of the dominant political actor. The citizens remain excluded from the political process, as their role continues to be restricted to legitimising the government through the elections.¹⁰

A unique feature of the Polish constitutional crisis is that it also has a transitional justice dimension. According to Marcin Matczak, the current government deeply mistrusts the 1997 Polish Constitution,¹¹ seeing it as an impunity instrument enacted in bad faith to protect the beneficiaries of communism from substantive justice using procedural justice as an excuse.¹² This mistrust had been even deeper with regards to the pre-2015 Polish Constitutional Court, which interpreted constitutional provisions as imposing certain limits on transitional justice measures. Because of the PCC case law in transitional justice cases, the Law and Justice leader Jarosław Kaczyński had dubbed the Court a bastion defending the post-transitional system in which the communist elite allegedly maintained power and privileges. His political fraction also coined the term ‘legal impossibilism’ which is generally used to refer to strict constitutional constraints supposedly stopping the parliamentary majority from introducing reforms necessary for the proper functioning of the state, including those that seek to overcome the legacy of the

⁵ Marcin Matczak, ‘Poland: From Paradigm to Pariah? Facts and Interpretations of Polish Constitutional Crisis’ (12 March 2018) <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3138541>> accessed 23 February 2022. For a description of some of the procedural requirements formulated in the PCC rulings see points 2.1-2.3 below. For more on the crisis see eg Aleksandra Kustra, ‘Poland’s Constitutional Crisis. From Court-packing Agenda to Denial of Constitutional Court’s Judgments’ (2016) 12 *Toruńskie Studia Polsko-Włoskie XII – Studi Polacco-Italiani Di Toruń* 343; Grażyna Skąpska, ‘The decline of liberal constitutionalism in East Central Europe’ in: Peeter Vihalemm, Anu Masso and Signe Opermann (eds), *The Routledge International Handbook of European Social Transformations* (Routledge 2018).

⁶ Adam Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism or New Constitutionalism’ (2019) 1 *Krytyka Prawa* 43, 44 (hereafter Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism’).

⁷ Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism’ (n 6) 51.

⁸ Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism’ (n 6) 54.

⁹ Adam Sulikowski, ‘Trybunał Konstytucyjny a polityczność. O konsekwencjach upadku pewnego mitu’ (2016) 4 *Państwo i Prawo* 3.

¹⁰ Maciej Pichlak, ‘Polskie spory między populistycznym a prawnym konstytucjonalizmem wobec refleksyjności konstytucji’ (2022) 1 *Archiwum Filozofii Prawa i Filozofii Społecznej* 63, 69-70. For a similar point see Paul Blokker, ‘Populism as a constitutional project’ (2019) 2 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 536.

¹¹ The Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 2 April 1997 (OJ 1997, No. 78, item. 483).

¹² Matczak (n 5) 9–12

communist past.¹³ The Supreme Court transitional justice rulings were subject to similar criticism. This critique was used by the government to justify the provisions reshaping the judicial branch, some of which were presented by their supporters as decommunization measures.¹⁴ Regardless of whether these claims were rational or sincere, this rhetoric shows that the Polish rule of law crisis has also a strong transitional justice dimension.¹⁵

In this chapter, I further explore the relations between the Polish constitutional crisis and transitional justice. I begin with the analysis of the normative transitional justice framework of Polish legal constitutionalism. This is a fact-checking enterprise, which aims to verify the claim that constitutional restrictions in this sphere were so strict that they amounted to legal impossibilism. Next, I identify possible inspirations which may have informed the transitional justice constitutional framework in order to assess whether, as some scholars state, Polish constitutionalism simply imitated Western ideas. Finally, in order to trace the origins of the Polish constitutional crisis, I examine the spectrum of alternative transitional justice responses, including the ones supported by the current government. In the end I claim that the belief in legal impossibilism in the transitional justice domain is rooted in a specific understanding of the objectives of political transition. According to the government, such a transformation must involve a fundamental change in social hierarchy, including an exchange of elites. The belief that liberal constitutionalism prevented this change serves as one of the pillars of the current Polish counter-constitutionalism.

2. Polish Transitional Justice Framework and Legal Impossibilism

In Poland, constitutional provisions related to transitional justice are scarce. A 1989 amendment¹⁶ to the 1952 Polish Constitution introduced the principle of democratic state governed by the rule of law and the principle of social justice to the legal system (this regulation was later repeated in the 1997 Polish Constitution). While the law also repealed provisions burdened with communist ideology, changed the name of the State, and altered the national coat of arms, additional past-oriented provisions were not implemented until the new Polish Constitution was enacted in 1997. Its preamble refers to 1989 as a year when Poland regained ‘the possibility of a sovereign and democratic determination of its fate’ and recalls ‘bitter

¹³ For other uses of the term see: Katarzyna Krzyżanowska, ‘Legal impossibilism versus the rule of law’, *Review of Democracy*, 29 June 2021, <<https://revdem.ceu.edu/2021/06/29/legal-impossibilism-versus-the-rule-of-law/>> accessed 13 September 2022.

¹⁴ For example, the statement of purpose of the SC Act, which allowed for the removal of all SC judges, provided a list of eleven rulings deemed especially unfair: seven of them concerned transitional justice, including five regarding lustration. The bill was vetoed and did not go into force. For a description of the SC rulings see: Michał Krotoszyński, ‘Transitional Justice and the Constitutional Crisis: The Case of Poland (2015–2019)’ (2019) 3 *Archiwum Filozofii Prawa i Filozofii Społecznej* 22, 32-33 (hereafter Krotoszyński, ‘Transitional Justice’).

¹⁵ See also Krotoszyński, ‘Transitional Justice’ (n 14).

¹⁶ Polish People’s Republic Constitution Amendment Act of 29 December 1989 (OJ No. 75, item 444).

experiences of the times when fundamental freedoms and human rights were violated' in Poland. The Constitution bans political parties and other organisations whose programmes are based upon totalitarian methods and practices of nazism, fascism or communism (Article 13). It also includes the *nullum crimen sine lege* principle, but it states that this principle does not prohibit punishing acts which, while domestically legal, were crimes under international law (Article 42(1)). Finally, the Constitution stipulates that there is no statute of limitations for war crimes and crimes against humanity (Article 43) and that the period of limitation does not run when a crime committed by a public official in the performance of their duties is not prosecuted for political reasons (Article 44).

Due to the lack of more extensive constitutional regulations, it was down to the PCC to establish a normative framework with regards to dealing with the past. This is not an exceptional case: in post-communist countries a normative shift towards liberal democracy was to a large extent carried out through constitutional courts rulings, and especially through their interpretation of the rule of law principle. This principle was incorporated into constitutions of almost all post-communist countries,¹⁷ but due to its general character its precise meaning in each of the states had to be determined through constitutional adjudication.¹⁸

That this meaning was in no way fixed is most evident in two well-known rulings of Eastern European constitutional courts, both related to laws lifting or prolonging statutes of limitation for criminal acts committed during the communist era and not prosecuted for political reasons. In 1992 the Hungarian Constitutional Court ("HCC") declared such a provision unconstitutional.¹⁹ Drawing on a somewhat paradoxical notion of 'the revolution of the rule of law', the HCC stated that: 'A State under the rule of law cannot be created by undermining the rule of law. The security of the law based on formal and objective principles is more important than the necessarily partial and subjective justice'.²⁰ According to the ruling, 'if the statute of limitations had run its course, the offender acquires the right as a legal subject not to be punished'²¹ – and the rule of law demands that this trust in one's impunity be protected. Therefore, lifting or extending the statute of limitations violates the principle of legal certainty,

¹⁷ Theodor Schweisfurth and Ralf Alleweldt, 'New Constitutional Structures in Central and Eastern Europe' (1998) 24 *Review of Central and East European Law* 289, 307.

¹⁸ For more on a role of constitutional courts in post-communist countries see eg: Ruti Teitel, 'Post-Communist Constitutionalism: A Transitional Perspective' (1994) 26 *Columbia Human Rights Law Review* 167; Ruti Teitel, *Transitional Justice* (OUP 2000) 191-211; Wojciech Sadurski, *Rights Before Courts: A Study of Constitutional Courts in Postcommunist States of Central and Eastern Europe* (Springer 2005) (hereafter Sadurski, *Rights*).

¹⁹ HCC Judgement of 5 March 1992, No. 2086/A/1991/14. Available in English in: Neil J. Kritz (ed), *Transitional Justice: How Emerging Democracies Reckon with Former Regimes. Volume III: Laws, Rulings, and Reports* (United States Institute of Peace Press 1995) 629-640).

²⁰ Kritz (n 19), 633.

²¹ Kritz (n 19), 638.

a core part of the formal aspect of the rule of law which must be protected even in the unique historical circumstances of transition.²²

On the other hand, a year later, the Czech Constitutional Court (“CzCC”) upheld a similar provision.²³ The CzCC relied on a more substantive understanding of the rule of law. According to the Court, even though the principle of legality is an important constitutional virtue, it should not be understood only formally: its interpretation and application should follow its purpose and respect democratic values. The rule of law cannot protect the impunity of communist perpetrators against just demands for their prosecution, as such an immunity would threaten the legitimacy of a new political system.²⁴

These two paradigmatic understandings of the rule of law can serve as a background against which the rulings of the PCC will be examined. Below, I concentrate on the PCC cases regarding the most salient areas of Polish transitional justice: lustration, the reduction of pensions, and the prosecution of communist crimes. As I discuss below, this analysis does not support the claim that legal impossibilism existed in the transitional justice sphere.²⁵

2.1. Lustration

The first judgement in which the PCC dealt with lustration was related to the 1992 parliamentary resolution ordering the Minister of Internal Affairs to present a list of top government officials, including members of parliament, who between 1945 and 1990 collaborated with the communist secret service.²⁶ This unverified list, which included the names of 66 people, was leaked to the press. Its publication led to a downfall of Jan Olszewski coalition government, part of which was Kaczyński’s Centre Agreement Party. The resolution itself was invalidated by the PCC on both formal and substantive grounds.²⁷ On the formal level, the act was found unconstitutional due to violations of parliamentary procedure, the lack of statutory form and the vagueness of its provisions. This last flaw – together with the absence of procedural guarantees for the accused – was also found to violate the rule of law due to its impact on individual rights. According to the PCC, the above defects meant the resolution itself, regardless of the way it was applied, ‘threatened to violate human dignity’ by not protecting

²² The HCC accepted the prosecution of crimes under international law, as these are not subject to the statute of limitations. See: Sadurski, *Rights* (n 18) 253.

²³ CzCC Judgement of 21 December 1993, Pl. ÚS 19/93. Available in English at: <https://www.usoud.cz/fileadmin/user_upload/ustavni_soud_www/Decisions/pdf/Pl%20US%2019-93.pdf> accessed 6 March 2022.

²⁴ For more on these two rulings see Sadurski, *Rights* (n 18) 249-258.

²⁵ Points 2.1-2.3 are partly based on: Michał Krotoszyński, *Modele sprawiedliwości tranzycyjnej* (Wydawnictwo Naukowe UAM 2017) 250-255.

²⁶ Resolution of Polish Sejm of 28 May 1992 (M.P. No. 16 item 116).

²⁷ PCC Ruling of 19 June 1992, U 6/92 (OTK 1992 part I, item 13).

personal rights.²⁸ Thus, formal aspects of the rule of law were seen as guarantees of the more substantive ones. Still, the requirements introduced in the ruling were very basic and rather easy to fulfil by law-makers.

In 1997 Polish Lustration Law²⁹ was passed with the votes of agrarian Polish People's Party, liberal Freedom Union and social-democratic Labour Union. In contrast to Czech or German regulations, which banned certain categories of people – such as top government officials, members of the communist party, or those tied to communist secret police – from holding specific positions in democratic public life (“decommunization”), Polish lustration has been devised as a historical clarification mechanism. Those subject to lustration are therefore required to submit a statement on whether they were officers or employees of the communist secret service, or knowingly and secretly collaborated with it. Only if this declaration proves to be false, the lustration liar is banned from holding certain public positions. Even though in 2006 the Law and Justice government enacted new, broader lustration law³⁰, the vetting model remained virtually unchanged.³¹

In 1998 the PCC upheld the constitutionality of the 1997 Lustration Act, invalidating only two minor provisions.³² The Court stated that lustration is generally consistent with both the rule of law and international standards, as long as its goal is to protect democracy and human rights, and not to punish those with a communist past. However, in order to comply with the rule of law, lustration provisions must be precise and the procedure needs to protect the rights of an individual.³³ To ensure such protection, the Court formulated a binding definition of collaboration: it had to be, *inter alia*, secret, conscious, and real.³⁴ Thus, merely signing a declaration of collaboration was not sufficient: there had to be proof of an actual cooperation, whether fruitful or not. This definition directly influenced the outcomes of many lustration cases. It protected those who, despite having been listed in the archives, had in fact never cooperated with the communist secret service. Yet, as many of the files had been destroyed in

²⁸ U 6/92, para. 44. Paragraph numbers are given after the PCC online judgements database (ipo.trybunal.gov.pl).

²⁹ Act of 11 April 1997 on Disclosing Work for, Service in, or Collaboration with State's Security Services Between 1944 and 1990 by Persons Exercising Public Functions (consolidated text: OJ 1999 No. 42 item 428).

³⁰ Act of 18 October 2006 on the Disclosure of Information on Documents of State Security Agencies from Years 1944–1990 and the Content of These Documents (consolidated text: OJ 2021 item 1633).

³¹ For an overview of the history of Polish lustration see eg Adam Czarnota, 'The Politics of the Lustration Law in Poland, 1989 – 2006' in Alexander Mayer-Rieckh and Pablo de Greiff (eds), *Justice as Prevention: Vetting Public Employees in Transitional Societies* (Social Science Research Council 2007) 222-258; Michał Krotoszyński, 'Polish lustration and the models of transitional justice' (2014) 3 Adam Mickiewicz University Law Review 199.

³² PCC Judgement of 10 November 1998, K 39/97 (OTK 1998 No. 6, item 99).

³³ K 39/97, paras. 88-96, 103-104

³⁴ K 39/97, para. 107.

1989, it also introduced an evidentiary threshold that may have been impossible to meet even in case of some real collaborators.

In 2003, the PCC invalidated an amendment enacted by the government of the post-communist Democratic Left Alliance and the Labour Union which had altered the definition of collaboration in a way that it no longer covered gathering or providing data as a part of intelligence, counterintelligence, and border protection tasks. As the internal structure of the communist secret service was heavily complicated, it is notoriously difficult to distinguish those duties from the actions targeting democratic opposition. According to the PCC, this ambiguity violated the rule of law's formal requirements, as the vetted had no straightforward way to assess whether their actions had fallen within the scope of the statutory exception: from their point of view, the outcome of lustration proceedings could not be foreseen. Thus, the PCC yet again invalidated a provision due to the possible infringement of the rights of the vetted; interestingly though, the ruling meant that the definition of collaboration expanded significantly.³⁵ Finally, in a manner similar to its Czech counterpart, the PCC claimed that the continuity of the Polish State after the democratic transition did not mean that the axiological basis of the State and its legal system remained unchanged. On the contrary, the 1989 constitutional amendment discussed above was a direct proof of a clean break with the past on the axiological level.³⁶ Even if this part of the judgement seems rather detached from the rest of the arguments, it shows dedication to a more substantive understanding of the rule of law.

The PCC's judgement on the 2006 Lustration Act (enacted by the Law and Justice government) is by far the most thorough review of the Polish lustration regulations up to date. In 2007, the PCC invalidated a large part of the law. The Court reiterated that lustration can be consistent with the rule of law, as long as its goal is to protect democratization and human rights, the restriction of individual rights is proportional, and the procedural guarantees are met.³⁷ However, many provisions were found to breach exactly these rules, while other infringed on equality or the right to informational self-determination.³⁸ According to the PCC, the act also violated formal aspects of the rule of law. Many provisions were invalidated because their imprecision or arbitrary nature infringed on the principle of proper legislation.³⁹ The principle was also violated by regulations which gave no discretion to disciplinary courts in

³⁵ Other reasons for invalidation included the violation of the equality principle and citizens' right to obtain information on persons in public functions. PCC Judgement of 28 May 2003, K 44/02 (OTK ZU 2003, No. 5A, item 44), paras. 48-82.

³⁶ K 44/02, para. 46.

³⁷ PCC Judgement of 11 May 2007, K 2/07 (OTK-A 2007, No. 5, item 48), paras. 263-265, 281, 285.

³⁸ K 2/07, paras. 381-414, 432, 435-443, 472-473, 476-484.

³⁹ K 2/07, paras. 372-380, 407, 429. The principle of proper legislation was inferred by the PCC from the principle of democratic state governed by the rule of law. It requires legal provisions to be, *inter alia*, clear, precise, and rational. See e.g. PCC Judgement of 30 October 2001, K 33/00 (OTK ZU 2001, No. 7, item 217), para. 45.

choosing how to punish lustration liars, and ordered their removal from legal professions: the PCC argued that without such discretion, the power of a disciplinary court is merely a façade.⁴⁰ Finally, an amendment to the 1998 Act on the Institute of National Remembrance⁴¹ (“IPN”) was found to have breached the requirement for a law to be public. Its provisions ordered the publication of a catalogue of communist secret service agents and collaborators, but their categories could not be properly understood without using secret instructions of communist security agencies, which cannot be treated as a source of law.⁴² The PCC’s extensive reasoning in this case became a core of Polish *acquis constitutionnel* with regards to lustration: while this framework was widely accepted among liberal and left-wing social actors, the ruling was heavily criticized by the Law and Justice politicians and their supporters. It was also after this judgement that the term ‘legal impossibilism’ started to be used in the public discourse by the political right. However, even though the PCC framework was indeed robust, lustration was still possible: for instance, although the Court restricted lustration to the public sphere, its scope was still broader compared to pre-2006 regulations.

Finally, in 2015 the PCC deemed unconstitutional the absence of a duty to waive judicial immunity before launching lustration proceedings. The Court claimed that the lustration of judges is an instrument of ensuring their high moral standards and judicial independence, both necessary for the rule of law and human rights protection. However, as launching lustration proceedings marks the vetted with a social stigma, judicial independence cannot be protected if these are instigated without due consideration – and the need to waive judicial immunity is a tool to ensure such restraint.⁴³

The PCC case law shows an ongoing tension between the demands for lustration, understandable in a young democracy, and the need to ensure that this process is carried out in line with the rule of law. While the PCC stressed in each ruling that lustration is fully compatible with the rule of law, it also used its judgements to create an *acquis constitutionnel* in this regard. This framework was often based on formal aspects of the rule of law, due to their direct impact on the protection of individual rights. The PCC also sought to ensure that lustration did not restrict these rights in a disproportionate way. While the framework created by the Court was comprehensive and detailed, it did not render lustration impossible. In fact, this framework was even more permissive regarding other transitional justice measures, to which I now turn.

⁴⁰ The provisions also violated the principle of proportionality. K 2/07, paras. 442-443.

⁴¹ Act of 18 December 1998 on the Institute of National Remembrance – Commission for the Prosecution of Crimes Against the Polish Nation (consolidated text: OJ 2021 item 177).

⁴² K 2/07, paras. 358-366, 371.

⁴³ PCC Judgement of 2 April 2015, P 31/12 (OTK ZU 2015, No. 4A, item 44), paras. 123-152.

2.2. Reduction of Pensions

On 1 January 2010 a statute enacted by the Civic Platform and the Law and Justice Party lowered retirement pensions of former communist security service officers and members of the Military Council of National Salvation (WRON), a military junta which ruled the country during the 1981-1983 martial law. In case of the former group, the pensions were reduced for each year of service in the communist security forces, while the pensions of WRON members were decreased for each year of army service starting from 8 May 1945.⁴⁴

The reduction was challenged before the PCC, which in its 2010 judgement upheld the law, finding only one provision partly unconstitutional. According to the PCC, the actions of WRON and communist secret police were fundamentally inconsistent with current constitutional values and the lawmaker had a right to reduce unjust retirement privileges enjoyed by their former members.⁴⁵ As recalculated pensions were on average still higher than the average ordinary pension – and therefore (high) above the social minimum – the Court decided that the law was proportional and did not infringe on human dignity or the core of the right to social security.⁴⁶ The act did not impose collective responsibility either: it was not repressive, as it involved no sanctions, but merely revoked privileges.⁴⁷ It was also consistent with the equality principle, though with one exception: the PCC decided that the reduction of pensions of WRON members for the years of army service prior to the martial law was discriminatory and unconstitutional, as in those years future junta members did not differ in any way from other professional Polish soldiers.⁴⁸

Finally, the law did not violate the doctrine of acquired rights. According to the PCC, even if an officer of the communist secret service passed the 1990 vetting and subsequently served in a similar agency in post-transitional Poland, this fact did not guarantee that the pensions for their service between 1944 and 1990 would remain intact. The retirement privileges were acquired unjustly and were therefore not protected: as the Court noted ‘guarantees of impunity and economic privileges granted by the dictatorship for service in institutions and bodies which used repressions cannot be treated as an element of justly acquired rights’.⁴⁹ Taking away those privileges did not violate the principle of legal certainty either:

⁴⁴ Act of 23 January 2009 Amending the Act on the Retirement Pensions of Professional Soldiers and Their Families and the Act on the Retirement Pensions of the Officers of the Police, the Internal Security Agency, the Foreign Intelligence Agency, the Military Counterintelligence Service, the Military Intelligence Service, the Central Anti-Corruption Bureau, the Border Guard, the State Protection Service, the State Fire Service, the Prison Service and their Families (OJ 2009, No. 24 item 145).

⁴⁵ PCC Judgement of 24 February 2010, K 6/09 (OTK ZU 2010, No. 2A, item 15), para. 388-442, 486.

⁴⁶ K 6/09, para. 492-541.

⁴⁷ K 6/09, para. 603-615.

⁴⁸ K 6/09, para. 581-602.

⁴⁹ K 6/09, para. 561.

between 1989 and 2009 the parliament repeatedly condemned the crimes of martial law, communist secret service and communism itself, and the 2010 reduction of pensions could hardly been a surprise.⁵⁰ The constitutional principle of social justice warranted the reduction of pensions: the PCC stressed that, in a democratic state governed by the rule of law, service in pre-transitional state institutions which violated human rights cannot justify claims to maintain retirement privileges.⁵¹ Therefore, according to the PCC, by reducing these unfairly acquired privileges in a proportionate manner, the lawgiver ‘acted justly’⁵².

In contrast to the Hungarian Constitutional Court, which focused on the protection of legal certainty and acquired rights (regardless whether they were acquired justly), the PCC based its ruling on more substantive considerations, including a resort to justice itself, in a manner somewhat similar to its Czech counterpart.

2.3. Prosecution of Communist Crimes

Article 9(1) of the Transitional Provisions to the Polish Criminal Code⁵³ stated that the statute of limitations for intentional offences against life, health, liberty or the administration of justice, punishable by prison sentences exceeding three years, which had been committed by public officers in the performance of their duties between 1944 and 1989, had started to run anew on 1 January 1990. Article 9(2) of the same act stipulated that any amnesties or indemnity acts enacted before 7 December 1989 did not apply to the perpetrators of these crimes. The latter provision was challenged before the PCC. Much like the Czech and Hungarian tribunals in the cases discussed above, it had to assess the extent to which a democratic state can use legislation to overcome obstacles to punishing the perpetrators of pre-transitional crimes.

In 1999 the PCC upheld the provision. According to the Court, the *lex retro non agit* principle did not prohibit from revoking an amnesty. The principle demanded that a person be punished only for an act which constituted an offence at the time it was committed; anything that happened after this point, including repealing an amnesty, was outside its scope. Therefore, the culprit had no right to remain unpunished.⁵⁴ However, even if such a right had existed, the contested regulation would have constituted ‘a statutory provision necessary in a democratic state governed by the rule of law for the protection of its security, public order, and public morals, which demand ending the impunity of perpetrators of crimes protected by a totalitarian

⁵⁰ K 6/09, para. 577.

⁵¹ K 6/09, para. 574.

⁵² K 6/09, para. 579.

⁵³ Act of 6 June 1997 – Transitional Provisions to the Criminal Code (OJ 1997 No. 88 item 554).

⁵⁴ PCC Judgement of 6 July 1999, P 2/99 (OTK ZU 1999 No. 5, item 103), para. 43-52.

state'.⁵⁵ Just like its Czech counterpart, the PCC understood public morals as 'a trust of citizens towards the state: towards its officials and towards the law it enacts, [the law] which binds both the citizens, regardless of their positions, and the State itself'.⁵⁶ Moreover, making the punishment of such perpetrators possible satisfied the constitutional principle of social justice, as it removed systematic injustice from the criminal law.⁵⁷ On a personal level, repealing such an amnesty also served human dignity, which demands that all people were treated equally and impartially. In a rather mysterious passage, the PCC claimed that 'justice which is present while combating impunity should be free of biased interests and forms, and of random force; it should be a justice which punishes, but does not avenge. In this sense, justice is stronger even than law'.⁵⁸

Even though both Hungarian and Polish constitutional courts based their rulings on the *lex retro non agit* principle, their interpretation could not differ more. The PCC rejected the wide understanding of the principle rooted in the struggle for legal certainty. Even though it did stress the importance of non-retroactivity of criminal law, the Court interpreted the principle in a narrow way. This allowed the PCC to refer directly to the principles of substantive justice: an approach somewhat similar to the one chosen by the Czech Constitutional Court.

2.4. The Question of Legal Impossibilism

In an op-ed published shortly after the 2007 PCC lustration ruling, Krystyna Pawłowicz – who four years later would become a Law and Justice member of parliament and in 2019 a PCC judge – criticized the judgement, calling it an example of the 'judicial review of the ruling party's political programme'. For Pawłowicz, invalidating a provision due to its conflict with a general clause (such as the rule of law) meant that the ruling was not based on strictly legal criteria but rather on an assessment of legislation's goals, subjective and dependent on the 'worldviews and sympathies' of the judges. As most of them were appointed by the opposition, Pawłowicz believed that the PCC could be used to 'overturn any important legislation enacted by a democratically elected majority', thus preventing 'the part of society that won the election from exercising power' and undermining the democratic nature of the Polish political system.⁵⁹ This belief in legal impossibilism is echoed in a 2011 book *Poland of Our Dreams*, in which Kaczyński also accused the PCC of illegitimately expanding its authority through the abuse of

⁵⁵ According to the Court, repealing an amnesty is also justified by the need to protect individual rights, as it opens a possibility of seeking damages in civil lawsuits. P 2/99, para. 59.

⁵⁶ P 2/99, para. 60.

⁵⁷ P 2/99, para. 63-66.

⁵⁸ P 2/99, para. 62.

⁵⁹ Krystyna Pawłowicz, 'Konstytucja pozwala na lustrację' *Rzeczpospolita* (29 June 2007).

general clauses.⁶⁰ For Kaczyński, this constitutional case law was an aspect of a deeper crisis, in which wide judicial interpretative powers transform the rule of law into the rule of lawyers, while an obligation to base government actions on an explicit statutory basis was a ‘specific type of legalism which ultimately leads to impossibilism’.⁶¹ There was a popular belief that transitional justice is one of the spheres in which these limitations were especially strict.

The above analysis does not support this claim. Polish constitutional provisions did not generate any explicit transitional justice restrictions, save perhaps the prohibition of retroactive criminal sanctions. Even though the PCC rulings in lustration cases did create a robust constitutional framework which significantly restricted the scope of lustration, introduced procedural guarantees, and created a high evidentiary threshold through the definition of collaboration, in no way did they make lustration impossible. On the contrary, the Court constantly reaffirmed that lustration itself was fully compatible with the rule of law. What is more, the judgements regarding the pre-2015 legislation on the reduction of pensions and the revoking of amnesties were highly permissive, and resorted to substantive justice in order to justify these regulations. Thus, a relative leniency of Polish transitional justice and its concentration on civil and political rights instead of economic ones – with minor and late exceptions regarding the reduction of retirement privileges – had more to do with the lawmakers’ restraint (and some of the Supreme Court rulings⁶²) than the judgements of the PCC.

Official statistics also confirm that transitional justice was possible. Up to 30 June 2021 nearly 125.000 out of circa 466.000 lustration statements were examined, out of which around 13.000 were questioned. Final rulings were announced in 2.144 court cases, and in 1.446 of them the statement was proven to be false.⁶³ As for the 2010 reduction of pensions, 38.563 decisions on their recalculation were issued; in 7.227 cases the pensions remained unchanged.⁶⁴ In addition to some early high-profile criminal cases, between 2000 and 2020 exactly 370 criminal proceedings were initiated against 558 people accused of communist crimes, out of which 162 were found guilty.⁶⁵ While this last number is arguably low, this had less to do with constitutional limitations and more with the inefficiency of criminal trials in general. Other pre-2015 transitional justice initiatives included the dissolution of the communist secret service,

⁶⁰ Jarosław Kaczyński, *Polska naszych marzeń* (Akapit 2011) 80.

⁶¹ Kaczyński (n 60) 79.

⁶² These include a notorious resolution which made it impossible to prosecute judges who during the martial law imposed retroactive criminal sanctions, on grounds that the communist legal system lacked the non-retroactivity principle, constitutional review, and clarity as to the status of international treaties. SC Resolution of 20 December 2007, I KZP 37/07 (OSNKW 2007 No. 12, item 86). See also Krotoszyński, ‘Transitional Justice’ (n 14) 32-33.

⁶³ Letter of 7 July 2021 from the IPN prosecutor (on file with author).

⁶⁴ K 6/09, paras. 530-531.

⁶⁵ Letter of 19 February 2020 from the Director of the IPN, no. IP 2.2020 (on file with author).

granting the access to its files, rehabilitation of former political prisoners, compensation for victims and memorialization.⁶⁶ Thus, Polish reckoning with the communist past was in general rather broad, even if it was also quite lenient.

From this perspective, the popular claim that transitional justice framework imposed by the PCC was so strict it amounted to legal impossibilism seems more like a myth than an honest and disinterested assessment of Polish *acquis constitutionnel*. Below I argue that the belief in legal impossibilism among the ruling elite stems from a particular (and controversial) interpretation of transition's major objectives. Before I move to this point, I first address another popular claim: that Polish transitional justice framework was simply a copy of standards developed in the West.

3. Transitional Rule of Law Framework: Inspirations

In this part of the paper, I use PCC judgements to identify potential inspirations which may have informed the transitional justice framework developed by the Court.⁶⁷ Contrary to popular beliefs, their minor role and increasingly adaptive use does not support the claim that Polish constitutionalism was a mere imitation of Western rule of law requirements.

3.1. Sources of Inspiration

In its transitional justice case law, the PCC referred to four kinds of documents which can be regarded as external sources of inspiration: (1) international soft law; (2) foreign legislation; (3) ECHR decisions, ECtHR judgements and rulings of other constitutional courts; and (4) literature on transitional justice and human rights.⁶⁸

In its 2010 ruling on the reduction of pensions, the PCC invoked international soft law – including resolutions and declarations of OSCE, the European Parliament and the Council of Europe Parliamentary Assembly (PACE) – to present a universal condemnation for the crimes of communism and common belief in the need to deal with its legacy in accordance with the

⁶⁶ See eg Frances Millard, *Transitional Justice in Poland: Memory and the Politics of the Past* (Bloomsbury 2021); Monika Nalepa and Michał Krotoszyński, 'Poland' in: Lavinia Stan and Nadya Nedelsky (eds), *Encyclopedia of Transitional Justice*, vol. 2 (2nd edn, CUP forthcoming).

⁶⁷ The list presented below is merely a catalogue of external sources that the PCC referred to in its reasoning. Whether these documents really inspired the judges is difficult to assess: some of them may have been invoked in written judgements to support the decisions previously made without them and their use was therefore purely rhetorical; in other cases some actual inspirations might have been missing from written rulings. The reasoning available for analysis belongs to the context of justification, not to the context of discovery: therefore, the list should be regarded only as a non-exclusive catalogue of possible inspirations.

⁶⁸ I exclude binding international treaties from my analysis, as the PCC is obliged to take them into account if the petitioners motion the Court to check the statute's compliance with these acts.

rule of law.⁶⁹ Legislation of other CEE countries and non-domestic rulings (ECHR decisions, ECtHR and German Constitutional Court judgements) were used by the PCC to provide a wider context of the legislation.⁷⁰ In lustration cases, the PCC referred to the ECtHR case law to strengthen its arguments that lustration laws should meet a legislative threshold expected from penal regulations,⁷¹ to argue that lustration of public figures does not violate their right to privacy,⁷² to claim that publication of lustration statements without a prior court judgement does not breach the right to fair trial,⁷³ and to comment on the temporary nature of lustration measures.⁷⁴ To prove this last point, the PCC also mentioned a Czech Constitutional Court judgement,⁷⁵ while a ruling of German *Bundesverfassungsgericht* was used to underline the importance of personal rights protection.⁷⁶ Finally, the PCC occasionally quoted transitional justice and human rights literature, mostly to remark on the nature of the implemented mechanisms and the position of victims and perpetrators.⁷⁷

The above documents played relatively minor roles in the PCC reasonings and seem to have been used only as additional sources of argumentation. None of them were used in more than two rulings. In this regard, they differ significantly from a 1996 PACE resolution, to which the PCC routinely referred in lustration cases, and which I explore below.

3.2. PACE 1996 Resolution and Guidelines

On 27 June 1996 the Council of Europe Parliamentary Assembly adopted a resolution on transitional justice in post-communist states.⁷⁸ The resolution and the attached guidelines⁷⁹ outlined the rule of law requirements that should be met by transitional justice measures, including criminal trials, lustration, restitution and reduction of pensions.

PACE soft law played an important role in the PCC lustration judgements. In 1998, the Court explicitly stated that ‘when it comes to lustration, constitutional requirements and, in particular, basic conditions of a democratic state governed by the rule of law, should be interpreted according to, inter alia, the aforementioned Council of Europe Parliamentary

⁶⁹ K 6/09, paras. 272-295.

⁷⁰ K 6/09, paras. 338-387.

⁷¹ K 2/07, para. 328; P 31/12, paras. 93, 129, 131.

⁷² PCC Judgement of 5 March 2003, K 7/01 (OTK ZU 2003, No. 3A, item 19), para. 80.

⁷³ K 7/01, paras. 144-148.

⁷⁴ P 31/12, para. 136.

⁷⁵ P 31/12, paras. 134-135.

⁷⁶ U 6/92, para. 35.

⁷⁷ U 6/92, para. 35; K 6/09, para. 561; P 31/12, paras. 130, 133.

⁷⁸ Resolution 1096 (1996) on Measures to Dismantle the Heritage of Former Communist Totalitarian Systems (hereafter also ‘PACE 1996 Resolution’).

⁷⁹ ‘Measures to dismantle the heritage of former communist totalitarian systems’ (1996) Report by Adrian Severin (Doc. 7568) (hereafter also ‘PACE 1996 Guidelines’).

Assembly resolution’.⁸⁰ In 2007 the PCC explained that even though the resolution is not legally binding, the Court should take it into account while interpreting both the statutes and the Constitution.⁸¹ The Tribunal also referred to these documents to argue that the goal of lustration measures is to protect democratic institutions, and that lustration is therefore a temporary measure.⁸² Finally, the PCC relied on the resolution and guidelines to articulate many of the requirements that lustration laws should fulfil: their individual application, protection against political misuse, and providing the vetted with full procedural guarantees, such as the right to a fair trial, the right to defence, and the presumption of lustration statement’s truthfulness.⁸³ The PCC reasoning in the 2007 ruling – which, as it was mentioned, is now considered a core of Polish *acquis constitutionnel* with regards to lustration – begins with a list of such requirements. This list, which covers thirteen short paragraphs,⁸⁴ is in fact a translation, either direct or indirect, of fragments of PACE 1996 Resolution and Guidelines, although no footnote is provided by the Court.⁸⁵

However, the resort to these acts is not unproblematic. PACE 1996 Resolution defines lustration as a process which aims to ‘exclude persons from exercising governmental power if they cannot be trusted to exercise it in compliance with democratic principles’.⁸⁶ Thus, lustration is understood as a mechanism of banning certain groups of people from holding public offices because of their involvement with the previous regime. This is understandable, as in 1996 most lustration laws, including the Czech and German ones, did involve such a disqualification. However, Polish lustration was created a year later as an instrument of historical clarification and does not involve sanctions for work or collaboration with the communist secret service; sanctions are imposed only for a lustration lie. Thus, some parts of the resolution and guidelines quoted by the PCC seem rather ill-fitted when it comes to Polish lustration. For instance, when lustration belongs to a historical clarification model, it seems out of place to claim that a state governed by the rule of law ‘has sufficient means at its disposal to ensure that the cause of justice is served and the guilty are punished’, that ‘[p]ersons who ordered, perpetrated, or significantly aided in perpetrating serious human rights violations may be barred from office’ and that there is ‘a need for an individual, and not collective, application

⁸⁰ K 39/97, para. 96.

⁸¹ K 2/07, para. 337.

⁸² K 2/07, para. 383.

⁸³ K 39/97, para. 89; P 31/12, para. 85.

⁸⁴ K 2/07, paras. 264-276.

⁸⁵ The PCC also referred to PACE 1996 Resolution to prove that the reduction of pensions is consistent with European standards. K 6/09, paras. 270-271, 488-490.

⁸⁶ PACE 1996 Resolution, para. 11.

of lustration laws'.⁸⁷ On the other hand, these conditions fit perfectly if lustration involves a ban on holding public offices, as in the Czech Republic.

These differences may be the reason why the PCC consciously omitted or modified some of the PACE guidelines to adjust them to Polish circumstances. First, the guidelines suggest that lustration should be administered by a special independent commission, that it should be restricted to non-elective positions of high importance – such as top government offices, law enforcement, security agencies, and the judiciary – and that it should not be imposed on people who acted under compulsion.⁸⁸ The PCC did not mention these recommendations and Polish lustration does not follow them either: it is conducted by courts (an arguably higher standard), it covers a wider array of public positions, including elective offices, and demands that even individuals who acted under compulsion confess to collaboration. Second, the guidelines recommend a rigorous lustration timeframe: vetting should take into account only acts conducted after 1 January 1980, the disqualification from office should not be longer than five years, and lustration measures should end no later than 31 December 1999, as by that time new democratic systems should be consolidated.⁸⁹ In its 2007 ruling, the PCC acknowledged that lustration should end when democratic system is firmly established and that sanctions imposed in the process should last only for a rational time, but no specific dates were given.⁹⁰ The court also ignored the 1980 threshold, and in fact Polish lustration covers employment, service and collaboration dating back to 22 July 1944. Finally, the guidelines advise that conscious collaborators should be vetted only if their actions actually harmed others and if this result was predictable.⁹¹ On the other hand, the PCC claimed that lustration is permissible if collaboration is clearly defined by a statute and is verified in a proper procedure.⁹² While the collaboration definition was introduced by the PCC in its 1998 ruling, it did not demand that the information provided by the individual cause the others any actual harm. To establish that collaboration took place, its real, genuine character was sufficient.

While some may argue that these differences suggest that the PCC's dedication to the rule of law was selective at best, another interpretation is possible. Restricting the number of those affected by lustration and introducing a rigorous vetting timeframe is arguably more important when lustration involves a ban on holding public offices – an important exception to otherwise equal right to participate in democratic public life. Yet, these constraints are less crucial when lustration is not a decommunization measure but a transparency mechanism

⁸⁷ PACE 1996 Resolution, paras. 4, 12; PACE 1996 Guidelines, pt. H; K 2/07, para. 265, 267, 274.

⁸⁸ PACE 1996 Guidelines, pts. A, D, E and L.

⁸⁹ PACE 1996 Guidelines, pts. G and J.

⁹⁰ K 2/07, para. 273.

⁹¹ PACE 1996 Guidelines, pt. K.

⁹² K 2/07, para. 275.

sanctioning only those who lack the integrity to speak openly about their past. Thus, one may argue that while the PCC took the resolution and its guidelines genuinely into account, the recommendations were adapted to fit a local context: a specific model of Polish lustration.

3.3. Between Imitation and Adaptation

According to some authors, the lack of knowledge on how constitutionalism, democracy and the rule of law work in practice was the reason why Polish transitional constitutionalism did not create its own independent form based on a local identity, but rather concentrated on a ‘mindless imitation of the West’ using ‘solutions [known] from books’ and resulting in ‘careless’ constitutional transplants.⁹³ This criticism seems similar to claims made by Kaczyński himself, who believed that legal impossibilism was created inter alia by transplanting conceptions aimed at tempering the communist system to the democratic one,⁹⁴ and who scolded Polish academia for its alleged peripherality, lack of intellectual independence and willingness to reproduce foreign ideas.⁹⁵

In the field of transitional justice such an imitative approach would surely mean a strict application of all the formal rule of law requirements, in a manner similar to the 1992 Hungarian Constitutional Court ruling. As Wojciech Sadurski points out,

The universalistic liberal ideal was used as a yardstick to judge the preparedness of the new democracies to join first the Council of Europe, and then the European Union. Western European political elites developed a stake in the integration of the ex-Communist East into the overarching political structures of the continent, not least for the sake of stability and peace in Europe. The criteria of “normal” democracy, untainted by any extraordinary measures related to its immediate non-democratic past, were instrumental in achieving these aims.⁹⁶

Nevertheless, many Polish scholars were well-aware of the problems faced when the rule of law is applied in a country undergoing a major political change. Suggestions that justice should have been done first, and that the introduction of the rule of law to the Polish legal system was therefore premature, were relatively rare.⁹⁷ Yet, even among those who believed that the transition (and transitional justice) had to be carried out in accordance with the rule of law, there were scholars who claimed that inconsistencies existing within the transitional legal system may deem fulfilling all the rule of law requirements impossible. This, however, did not

⁹³ Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism’ (n 6) 53-54.

⁹⁴ Kaczyński (n 60) 75-76, 103.

⁹⁵ Kaczyński (n 60) 41, 94-95.

⁹⁶ Sadurski, *Rights* (n 18) 232.

⁹⁷ In a modern literature this argument was used by Czarnota, ‘Populist Constitutionalism’ (n 6) 52.

release the lawmaker from an obligation to respect basic standards of the rule of law.⁹⁸ Apart from two radical solutions – to completely reject the rule of law for the time being, or to strictly follow all its requirements – a more moderate response was also possible.

The PCC's use of the PACE 1996 Resolution and Guidelines suggests that, in a similar manner, aside from a 'mindless imitation' of the Western constitutionalism and from creating a wholly independent one, there was also a third way: an adaptation of the rule of law framework to local circumstances. It is true that many constitutional ideas and practices were imported to Poland from the West. Yet, the way in which the PCC adapted the PACE resolution and guidelines to local conditions seems to indicate a certain dose of autonomy. It also suggests that, to a certain degree, Polish transitional justice framework was increasingly adaptive over time instead of merely imitative. This conclusion is further supported by PCC rulings on revoking amnesties and reduction of pensions which have departed far from a formalistic understanding of the rule of law. Therefore, more research is needed to assess whether this adaptive technique was used more often, before it can be proven that in fields other than transitional justice Polish constitutionalism was indeed purely imitative. In fact, if the rule of law requirements are understood as a part of (imported) legal tradition, it may be argued that some level of adaptation is always more probable than sole imitation. Even if an interpreter is dedicated to adhering to the tradition they received (as the PCC definitely was), the need to apply it to the case at hand is likely to cause modifications, and their character may be the result of the local legal tradition.⁹⁹ While this process may happen unintentionally, it may also be a conscious one, as in the case of the Polish transitional justice framework.

4. Transitional Justice Alternatives: Political Transformation as an Exchange of Elites

Despite an array of implemented transitional justice measures, there is a widespread belief that reckoning with the past was not possible due to the restrictive constitutional framework created by the PCC through the transplantation of Western rule of law standards. I have already argued that legal impossibilism conceived in this way is a myth. However, among the members and supporters of the current Polish government the belief in legal impossibilism in the transitional justice context is based on a specific understanding of the core objectives of political transformation. According to this way of thinking, the process of democratization must also involve a significant change in social hierarchy, including an exchange of elites. To illustrate this way of thinking, I now turn to the alternatives to the Polish transitional justice

⁹⁸ Sławomir Wronkowska, 'Czy Rzeczpospolita Polska jest państwem prawnym?' in Sławomira Wronkowska (ed), *Polskie dyskusje o państwie prawa* (Wydawnictwo Sejmowe 1995) 85-89.

⁹⁹ See Martin Krygier, 'Law as Tradition' (1986) 5(2) *Law and Philosophy* 237, 242-243 & 254.

model, which were possible both at the level of constitutional adjudication and constitutional provisions themselves.

4.1. Dissenting opinions

Transitional justice cases are as important, as they are notoriously hard. They involve dilemmas of not only legal, but also moral and political nature. Therefore, one may expect that many of the constitutional judgements in transitional justice cases will not be unanimous. The table below proves that this is indeed the case when it comes to the PCC rulings.

Case type	Lustration						Reduction of pensions	Amn-esty
	U 6/92	K 39/97	K 7/01	K 44/02	K 2/07	P 31/12	K 6/09	P 2/99
No. of judges deciding the case	10	12	15	14	11	5	14	5
No. of dissenting opinions	1	4	1	4	9 (100)	1	5 ⁽¹⁰¹⁾	0
<i>supporting decisions that would have resulted in harsher transitional justice measures</i>	1	3	-	-	4	1	-	-
<i>supporting decisions that would have resulted in more lenient transitional justice measures</i>	-	1	1	4	5	-	5	-

Some of the dissenting opinions indicate that in case of lustration harsher reckoning with the communist past was possible. In these opinions judges often referred to substantive values, including justice itself. A separate opinion to the PCC judgement on the 1992 parliamentary resolution questioned the Court's assumption that its application had to violate the personal rights of those included on the list of communist secret service collaborators. According to Judge Łączkowski, this conclusion could not be defended on 'neither legal nor ethical grounds': if information on past collaboration was accurate, it could not harm a good name of former agents – and even if it would, 'ethical reasons, as well as the principles of justice and equality, suggest that defending the rights of the repressed should be a priority'¹⁰². In the 1998 ruling three opinions defended the constitutionality of a provision ordering a removal of a lustration liar from the list of presidential candidates through an administrative act of an election committee. One of the judges argued that a lack of such sanction would violate public morality and the principle of the rule of law. Allowing a lustration liar to become the president would be fatal for the authority of state institutions – 'a principal value in a state governed by the rule of law'. Thus, 'rule of law procedural values' cannot be contrasted with necessary

¹⁰⁰ Four of the dissenting opinions questioned only the constitutionality of the collaboration definition, one claimed that the statute should be entirely invalidated, and four defended constitutionality of its various provisions. The latter two are discussed below.

¹⁰¹ Additionally, one separate opinion disagreed with parts of the justification, but agreed with the ruling on merits.

¹⁰² Dissenting opinion of Judge Wojciech Łączkowski: U 6/92, para. 77.

personal virtues: honesty, integrity, and respect for the law and fellow citizens. The first virtue is especially important as ‘the respect for the government and the law has always relied on truth’.¹⁰³

Four dissenting opinions defended constitutionality of the major part of the 2006 Lustration Law. Some of the judges claimed that the PCC was too eager to interfere with the relative autonomy of the legislator. Even when such an intervention was warranted, constitutionality of many provisions could easily be obtained through their binding interpretation.¹⁰⁴ What is more, two opinions demonstrated a more substantive understanding of the rule of law. According to them, a democratic state not only needs appropriate state institutions, but it also ‘needs to be based on clear axiological and moral standards’¹⁰⁵. Thus, in such a state, ‘the legislator has a duty to deal with a difficult past for the good of society’ and to ensure proper operation of state institutions: lustration laws can be instruments of this change, if they are based on virtues such as truth, memory, human dignity and freedom.¹⁰⁶ According to Judge Liszcz, these exceptional transitional circumstances ‘justify the need for a gradation and more liberal application of constitutional constraints’ designed for stable democracies. This is because as the time passes, ‘dealing with the past in a manner that is fully consistent with all constitutional requirements will be more and more difficult, if at all possible’.¹⁰⁷

However, dissenting opinions also show that Polish transitional justice could have been much more restricted. A separate opinion to the 1998 PCC judgement claimed that because of the social stigma associated with the ties to the communist secret service, the need to confess to such connections is equal with self-denunciation and therefore contrary to the rule of law.¹⁰⁸ If this opinion prevailed, the Polish model of lustration would not be possible. Subsequent dissenting opinions questioned overall constitutionality of lustration¹⁰⁹ or that it also covered individuals who did not partake in core activities of the communist secret service.¹¹⁰ Finally, five dissenting opinions claimed that the 2010 reduction of pensions was unconstitutional. According to the judges, officers who in democratic Poland passed the 1990 vetting and were re-employed in security agencies had a right to expect that their pensions will remain intact. Therefore, the law violated their vested rights, legal security and trust towards the state, which

¹⁰³ Dissenting opinion of Judge Marian Zdyb: K 39/97, paras. 191-225. Quotes: paras. 200, 214.

¹⁰⁴ Dissenting opinion of Judge Maria Gintowt-Jankowicz: K 2/07, paras. 626-657.

¹⁰⁵ Dissenting opinion of Judge Teresa Liszcz: K 2/07, para. 758.

¹⁰⁶ Dissenting opinion of Judge Zbigniew Cieślak: K 2/07, paras. 583, 623.

¹⁰⁷ Dissenting opinion of Judge Teresa Liszcz: K 2/07, para. 766.

¹⁰⁸ Dissenting opinion of Judge Zdzisław Czeszejko-Sochacki: K 39/97, paras. 148-164.

¹⁰⁹ Dissenting opinions of Judge Bohdan Zdziennicki: K 44/02, paras. 102-140; K 2/07, paras. 853-969.

¹¹⁰ Dissenting opinion of Judge Bohdan Zdziennicki: K 7/01, paras. 150-176.

are all protected under the rule of law. The opinions also argued that the act lacked individualization, was disproportionate and infringed on the principle of proper legislation.¹¹¹

The authors of these opinions preferred an even stricter constitutional framework. According to Judge Zdziennicki, transitional justice regulations need to comply with all the rule of law requirements, as ‘there are no special constitutional provisions for dealing with people associated with the former system of government’.¹¹² His own list of acceptable solutions seems relatively short and does not include the politics of memory: in another ruling Zdziennicki claims that ‘the law, by its very nature, cannot impose a specific vision of the past and draw legal consequences from such an assessment’.¹¹³ Whether this neutrality is observed or not, the rule of law requirements need to be fulfilled in order to safeguard individual rights. Thus, Judge Jamróz warns against pursuing justice at the expense of the rule of law:

I do not accept ... adjudication which relies on ‘pure’ social justice and is inspired by political and moral convictions, but which disregards constitutional principles developed in the Court’s jurisprudence, [the principles] which reflect modern, well-established standards of a democratic state governed by the rule of law. This method creates a risk of turning the Tribunal from a court of law to a court of social justice.¹¹⁴

Comparing the number of judges with the number of dissenting opinions suggests that if the composition of the PCC’s adjudicating panels was partially different, some of the Court’s pivotal decisions (including the ones in transitional justice cases) may have gone in another direction. This trivial truth explains why altering the personal composition of judicial branch has been such an important factor in the Polish rule of law crisis. If one ‘sees people rather than institutions’ then reshaping the judiciary ‘is not an attempt to repair and strengthen the institutions (...) but above all to change the cadres’.¹¹⁵ As Jarosław Kaczyński himself explained: ‘To change Poland, one needs the right people’.¹¹⁶

4.2. Alternative constitutional provisions

Transitional justice provisions are not abundant in the 1997 Polish Constitution, and they were similarly absent in its drafts prepared by political actors.¹¹⁷ One significant exception was Article 29 of the constitutional draft submitted by Kaczyński’s Centre Agreement Party,

¹¹¹ Dissenting opinions of Judges: Adam Jamróz, Ewa Łętowska, Marek Mazurkiewicz, Mirosław Wyrzykowski, and Bohdan Zdziennicki: K 6/09, paras. 617-921.

¹¹² Dissenting opinion of Judge Bohdan Zdziennicki: K 44/02, para. 107.

¹¹³ Dissenting opinion of Judge Bohdan Zdziennicki: K 2/07, paras. 915, 940.

¹¹⁴ Dissenting opinion of Judge Adam Jamróz: K 6/09, para. 670.

¹¹⁵ Martin Krygier, ‘The Challenge of Institutionalisation: Post-Communist ‘Transitions’, Populism, and the Rule of Law’ (2019) 3 *European Constitutional Law Review* 544,

¹¹⁶ Kaczyński (n 60) 91.

¹¹⁷ The drafts available in Polish in: *Komisja Konstytucyjna Zgromadzenia Narodowego. Projekty Konstytucji* (Wydawnictwo Sejmowe 1993) (hereafter ‘*Projekty Konstytucji*’).

which stipulated that a statute may provide an exemption from the *nullum crimen sine lege* principle with regards to acts which in a particularly severe way violated basic human rights and the rights of the Polish Nation.¹¹⁸

On the other hand, the so-called ‘civic draft’ of the constitution¹¹⁹ – prepared by experts, financed and managed by the Solidarity trade union, and signed by over one million of people¹²⁰ – included many transitional justice provisions. Article 26(2) ordered lustration of public officials and candidates for office. Article 161(1) stated that the provisions enabling reprivatization should be enacted within a year after the Constitution came into force. The same deadline was set for passing a statute on the vetting of judges (Article 163). Article 164 provided for a transfer of communist secret service files to the IPN and ordered that a law regulating access to them be adopted within a six-month period. However, only one provision made its way to the final text of the 1997 Constitution: Article 22 of the draft stated that there would be no statute of limitations for war crimes and crimes against humanity and that the proscription period would not run when a crime was not prosecuted for political reasons (see Articles 43 and 44 of the Polish basic law).

The popular draft and the above provisions are fondly remembered by the current ruling party. In 2017 a conference celebrating the alternative constitutional draft was held in the Polish Senate. In an opening speech, Kaczyński criticized the 1997 Polish Constitution, calling it ‘post-communist’ and accusing it of petrifying the existing social structure. On the other hand, the Law and Justice leader praised the popular draft. According to Kaczyński, it included ‘an ingenious idea’ which made it ‘fundamentally different’ from the current Polish constitution: through the provisions described above, the draft was effectively ‘abolishing post-communism’, in a way that ‘made it impossible to use the law for blocking such changes’.¹²¹

In fact, two Law and Justice constitution drafts – prepared in 2005 and 2010 – included some similar provisions. They both proclaimed the right to obtain information about the communist regime and individuals involved in its actions, tasked the IPN with fostering this right, and provided for lustration. Both drafts also banned individuals who eagerly fought against the democratic opposition from holding public offices, while the later one also explicitly introduced a ten-year period for vetting of judges. Finally, the 2005 draft ordered that a Truth and Justice Commission be created for a period of five years. The task of this commission was to investigate and disclose abuses of public positions occurring after 1989 in the interest of an

¹¹⁸ *Projekty Konstytucji*, 100.

¹¹⁹ Solidarity’s Popular Initiative Constitution Draft. Published in: *Co Tydzień Solidarność* (30 June 1994) 1.

¹²⁰ For an overview of the initiative see: Emilia Kowalewska, ‘Between civic and legal constitutionalism: Dynamics of Poland’s constitution-making projects of the 1990s’ (2020) 10(4) *Oñati Socio-Legal Series* 903.

¹²¹ See Jan Majchrowski (ed), *Konstytucja Solidarności* (Wydawnictwo Sejmowe 2018) 30-31.

individual or a group – a striking example of a mistrust towards the early years of the Polish democratic system.¹²²

4.3. Tuning the Piano: Transitional Justice and the Transformation of Social Hierarchies

The 2005 and 2010 Law and Justice drafts suggest that for this party ‘abolishing post-communism’ must involve removing the former elite from important positions in a democratic system. Without such a change, transitional justice is incomplete. Kaczyński makes this point in his 2011 book, describing four aspects of a successful transition: he states that while Poland was able to build democracy and capitalism, the lack of decommunization meant that it failed to create ‘a new state’ and ‘a new social hierarchy’.¹²³ Kaczyński describes the Round Table Agreements as the birth of the new elite, composed of the former members of communist nomenklatura – who during the transition either acquired or remained in control of a large part of national property – and some members of the democratic opposition. According to the Law and Justice Leader this meant that after 1989 the old elite maintained much of their control over Polish political and economic life.¹²⁴ Kaczyński seems deeply convinced that the lack of decommunization slowed down crucial reforms: he claims that if such a vetting would have taken place, ‘the GDP would be higher by circa 25 percent’, ‘more flats would have been built’ (he estimates the difference at two million!), the budget for higher education would be a couple of times bigger – and even that ‘more children would have been born’.¹²⁵ Therefore, for the Law and Justice leader, the lack of thorough screening is one of transition’s biggest mistakes, and some kind of retrospective vetting is still necessary to reshape the social order.¹²⁶

In order to ensure their effective and fair operation, such a vetting should cover inter alia state offices, security agencies, mass-media, banks, and courts.¹²⁷ While this does not necessarily mean a total purge, in order to induce social change the vetting should be both broad and deep. According to Kaczyński:

Power is a system of relations between people. If these relations are disrupted and those below are from a different faction than the ones in charge, then it may be said that the keys of the piano cannot reach to the strings. One plays from a new music sheet, but hears an old melody. This is how many institutions,

¹²² Articles 28, 147 and 166-166 of the 2005 Law and Justice Constitution Draft and Articles 29, 35, 191 and 192 of the 2010 Law and Justice Constitution Draft. Available at <<<https://oko.press/images/2017/10/PiS-projekt-konstytucji-2005.pdf>> and <<https://oko.press/images/2017/10/PiS-projekt-konstytucji-2010.pdf>>, accessed 5 May 2022).

¹²³ Kaczyński (n 60) 72-73.

¹²⁴ Kaczyński (n 60) 42-58. Jarosław Kaczyński, Michał Bichniewicz, Piotr M. Rudnicki, *Czas na zmiany. Rozmowa z Jarosławem Kaczyńskim* (2nd edn, Editions Spotkania 2014) 15-18, 133-194.

¹²⁵ Kaczyński (n 60) 82.

¹²⁶ Kaczyński (n 60) 108.

¹²⁷ Kaczyński, Bichniewicz, Rudnicki (n 124) 133-194.

including the television, work today. (...) This is why until this day it is no difference who plays the piano, because whatever they would play – what we hear is *The Internationale*.¹²⁸

Thus, for the Law and Justice leader, decommunization is crucial for inducing a transformation of the whole social hierarchy: it is a tool for an essential exchange of the public elite. It is only after such an exchange that political, economic, and social transformation is fully completed.¹²⁹

However, according to the current government such a transformation would not be possible under the 1997 Polish Constitution and the PCC case law. In 2011 Kaczyński claimed that in order to vet the judges, a constitutional amendment would be necessary¹³⁰ and that ‘an ostentatious screening’ conducted by the Truth and Justice Commission ‘could have been easily invalidated by the PCC’.¹³¹ It is therefore no coincidence that the Polish constitutional crisis began with the conflict between the government and the PCC, and that during the same period many decommunization provisions were also enacted.¹³² This is because under closer scrutiny legal impossibilism turns out to have a very particular meaning: in the context of political transformation it is understood as a restriction on the fundamental rearrangement of the social hierarchy – an interpretation very much rooted in specific beliefs about the core objectives of democratic transition.

It is true that a widespread disqualification of former communist elites has never been implemented in Poland. However, is the belief that such a process was impossible under Polish transitional justice framework justified? Even though no definite answer can be given, one should note that in 1990 vetting procedures were carried out with regards to the SC and to the former communist secret service, both resulting in significant personnel changes. While these regulations were not subject to constitutional review, there is no reason to believe the PCC would have held them contrary to the rule of law: in fact, the PACE 1996 Resolution and Guidelines explicitly allowed for such measures. Yet, as the years since the transition go by, it becomes more difficult for such provisions to pass the proportionality test. Thus, when the Law and Justice came to power in 2005 and 2015, it may have been indeed too late to introduce such a disqualification in a way consistent with constitutional requirements. Still, even if this proved to be true (which we shall never know), the lack of decommunization should still be considered

¹²⁸ Kaczyński, Bichniewicz, Rudnicki (n 124) 140.

¹²⁹ See also: Janusz Reykowski, ‘The Massive Exchange of Elites as a Mean of Formation of the Authoritarian Regime’ in: Jerzy J. Wiatr (ed), *New Authoritarianism: Challenges to Democracy in the 21st century* (Verlag Barbara Budrich 2019) 50-56.

¹³⁰ Kaczyński (n 60) 104.

¹³¹ Kaczyński (n 60) 107. The context suggests that screening is understood here as a disqualification mechanism.

¹³² Krotoszyński, ‘Transitional Justice’ (n 14) 26-27.

mainly a result of the lawmakers inactivity, for which the PCC can hardly be blamed. From this perspective, legal impossibilism is, at best, unproven – and possibly a myth as well.

5. Conclusions: Legal Impossibilism and Polish Counter-Constitutionalism

In her chapter on constitutional sociology, Kim Lane Scheppele describes successful constitutions as ones which ‘manage to create their own social life’.¹³³ Such constitutions reach beyond legal domain and are able to dominate social imaginary: they ‘shape social expectations and understandings, and come to be taken for granted’.¹³⁴ Scheppele understands constitutions as ‘fields of naturalised ideas’:¹³⁵ as long as they seem obvious and are unquestioned, even a serious economic or political crisis does not threaten the constitutional order. It is when a constitution is ‘fundamentally challenged’ and its ‘reality becomes questionable’ that social actors need to adjust the rules ‘to rescue its normality’: ‘[i]f they fail – or if they fail to try – constitutions can crumble’.¹³⁶

Constitution can become denaturalised through ideological competition. This competition is caused by counter-constitutions, defined by Scheppele as ‘alternative visions of constitutional order, grounded in different understandings of what a constitution is and should be’ which ‘reject the taken-for-granted constitutional vision already in place’.¹³⁷ Scheppele attributes the collapse of Hungarian liberal constitutionalism to the emergence of such a counter-constitutional narrative. This narrative presented the 1989 constitution as foreign, offered an alternative constitutional symbol (the Holy Crown of St Stephen, allegedly a ‘true’ Hungarian constitution) and created its own politics of memory.¹³⁸ Scheppele explains that:

Had the counter-constitutional ideas not been around to provide a ready-to-hand alternative conceptual frame, the 1989 constitution might have been harder to topple. But once an alternative constitutional conception came to be seen as legitimate by segments of the Hungarian population, it became impossible for the 1989 constitution to naturalise the political space any longer. The dominant constitutionalism ceased to hold, and the post-1989 constitutional order became easy to destroy because it was no longer accepted as real.¹³⁹

In the vast literature on the Polish constitution crisis, theories as to what caused the decline of liberal constitutionalism in this country differ significantly. The answers given by

¹³³ Kim Lane Scheppele, ‘The Social Lives of Constitutions’ in Paul Blokker and Chris Thornhill (eds), *Sociological Constitutionalism* (CUP 2017) 35.

¹³⁴ Scheppele (n 133) 35.

¹³⁵ Scheppele (n 133) 62.

¹³⁶ Scheppele (n 133) 56.

¹³⁷ Scheppele (n 133) 61.

¹³⁸ Scheppele (n 133) 61.

¹³⁹ Scheppele (n 133) 61.

Polish scholars are varied and include factors as different as the need for group identification, globalization and economic disparities, the fear of the migration crisis, and the dominance of legal positivism.¹⁴⁰ Many authors agree, however, that the lack of an entrenched democratic culture is one of the reasons of the crisis.¹⁴¹ While this may well be true, there is also an alternative explanation to consider: that a liberal vision of a political order was well-entrenched but became denaturalised when Polish counter-constitutionalism emerged.

Just like their Hungarian counterparts, Polish conservatives created an alternative constitutional imaginary. An alternate narrative on Polish democratization was formulated, in which the Round Table Agreements and ensuing peaceful transformation were presented not as a historical achievement, but as the original sin of the post-transitional social order: the birth of the new elite, composed of prominent members of the democratic opposition and the former communists. In this vision, the fact that the latter have been able to participate in democratic public life is not a liberal virtue, but proof that the transition was mainly superficial: a true transformation would have to include a fundamental change in social hierarchy, including an exchange of political and economic elites. According to counter-constitutionalists, this was unfortunately not possible, as the 1997 constitution (enacted by the new elite and infused with foreign ideas), the PCC and the rest of the judiciary guarded the post-transitional political, economic and social structure. One of ways in which they allegedly defended the system was the abuse of general clauses, including the rule of law. In this narrative, the constitutional order was designed to create a state of legal impossibilism, in which social hierarchies would remain intact. Thus, the belief in legal impossibilism which prevented the vetting of public sphere (including the judiciary) is central for this understanding of Polish transition. This interpretation serves to delegitimize liberal constitutionalism and to simultaneously present an alternative, in which the cadres are more important than the institutions and the procedures, and the exchange of elites becomes a prerequisite of a just and efficient state. While the Law and Justice counter-constitutionalism looks for alternative constitutional tokens (such as Solidarity's popular draft) and political symbols (such as the deposition from power of the Olszewski's government), it is ultimately also forward-looking, and promises a new, fair social order.

The role which the PCC and the courts play in this counter-constitutional vision explains why the implementation of the Law and Justice project began with changes in the personal composition of the judicial branch. There is, however, another lesson to be drawn from the analysis of Eastern European counter-constitutionalism. While it is tempting to look for

¹⁴⁰ See eg: Matczak (n 5) 9–21; Sadurski, *Poland's* (n 4) 162–191; Skąpska (n 5) 141–143; Michał Stambulski, 'Constitutional Populism and the Rule of Law in Poland' in: by Martin Krygier, Adam Czarnota and Wojciech Sadurski (eds), *Anti-Constitutional Populism* (CUP 2022) 346–351.

¹⁴¹ Skąpska (n 5) 142; Sadurski *Poland's* (n 4) 182–187.

straightforward, legal solutions to the rule of law crisis, these may not be sufficient in the long run. If Scheppele's diagnosis is right, then in order to respond to counter-constitutionalism in a permanent way, its narrative needs to be denaturalized and an alternative constitutional vision has to be present. While this vision may include a return to liberal constitutionalism, its imaginary has to be sufficiently deep to reinspire and altered enough to make up for its previous deficits; it must also include its own politics of memory. This is a huge and daunting task, but from the perspective of constitutional sociology a small-scale constitutional project may simply not be possible.

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